

TV Commercials and its influencing power on Buyers' Buying Decision

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Abstract

as these days, consumers have much spending and influencing power to make the purchase compare to past time. The purchase decision is the process of which consumers are gathering the information from different sources and their decision involves with many factors such as commercial, family members and other elements of purchasing process. Commercials is a communication method to inform, persuade and remind about the products/ services by the marketer through media. Television commercials have become a part of daily lives and reflected one of the most powerful means to influence the purchase decision. The objective of the study is to determine whether constant exposure of advertisement had a direct impact on shoppers' behaviour and to find out the effect of commercials on buying decision. A survey was conducted with 160 respondents using structured questionnaire manually and through online. The obtained data were studied with using suitable statistical tools. It was found that respondents were impressed, influenced from commercials and having the impact on their buying decisions

Key Words: Advertisement, Commercials, Buying Decision, Buyer Behavior

1. Introduction:

The Business is growing quicker than constantly ahead; marketers are as promoters regularly looking for innovative means to interact with their target audiences. TV commercial is effective and is efficient to influence the consumer-buying decision. According to Robertson (1980), the gradual increase in the broadcasting of advertisement causes the curiosity of how these ads affect a family and its purchasing behavior. The reason for this action is that consumer who watch ads are frequently attract to the goods that are being accelerated and encouraging them to hold of knowledge on something are required.

TV commercial is the impersonal communication of the information usually paid for it and convincing in reality of commodities, services or thoughts by distinguished patrons through the different means (Datta, 2008). The promoter intends to spread his ideas about the products and offering among the prospects. The popularization of the goods is hence, the primary object of promoting (Ramaswami & Namakumari, 2004). The preponderance of the marketers' uses mass media for theirs selling information. The selection of media is dependent on the type of the communication and the expected target audience (Etzet et al., 2008). Promoting product with all the marketing communication tools having the sufficient impact on viewers, though informing with the ad is one of the efficient tool of advertising and due to its mass reach. It can have the influence not simply the individual's attitude, habits, lifestyle, expression and in the long run, indeed the culture of the nation (Latif and Abideen, 2011). TV commercial cannot only change emotions but give the subliminal information. Broadcasting now appears to be universally and always perform exercising a far-reaching impact on the regular lives (Kotwal et al. 2008a). Television prevails the real efficient mechanism as transferring today's buyers, and it further is enormously valuable tools for adding value for customers to the image of the product.

Communicating by Television empowers marketers to expose and inform broad viewers regarding their business, goods, or services. It allows one to demonstrate the benefits of ownership. Electronic Communication channels attract to the people as well as this is one characteristic of it that presents it novel and different from various means. T.V. ad facilitates the productive individuals to interact by connecting act,

tones, sounds, coloring, character, and limelight background to show and express sentiments to the general and the broadly dispersed public. T.V. commercials usually play a role in either introducing a product or strengthening the awareness of the commodity and more reliable to obtain the goods. In common, concern there is a concern of progenitors and distinct societal players, that TV advertisement will have a contradictory, intentional or unintended, impact on consumers or shoppers (Burr and Burr 1977; Goldberg 1990). It is noted that it has influences on choice and their purchases (Hawkins et al., 2001). The study mentioned above is an attempt to see at Impact of Television Advertisements on consumers and to know their various impressions on selection of goods and on purchase decisions.

2. Review of Literature:

Here advertising has been taken as the promotion of awareness and an act of promotion is to attract target market or audience's attention. Advertising is a paid and non-personal communication through various media about the company's business, non-profit-oriented, product or predetermined idea Organization in a message intended to inform or persuade members of the target market" (Kurtz, 2008). Promotion can be performed through television, radio, magazines, banners, outdoor, newspapers, direct mail, websites and text messages. It called for a new ad format for the market another viral strategy recently by using a novel or a form of entertainment marketing message via the Internet (Krizan, Merrier, Logan, and Williams, 2008). According to Rossiter (1998), the functions of the ad refers. Advertising is not only to entertain the consumer, but it also uses to create the shopper attention. It is the way that effect, enhances the attractiveness of the firm desire for the product, and allowing the buyers of the market or the target consumer to be informed with the current information, knowledge, confident in their choice, and to change people's attitude in the product. That is commonly referred to as the target market arrangement known of Attention interest; stimulate desire and action to purchase to achieve the AIDA model.

According to the study, the television advertising depends on how the people loves television advertising, seems positively or negatively (Rossiter, 1979). Ads play a significant role in people lives through its brands and help them learn how to use them (Peter and Olson, 1994). In a one study it it was concluded that a advertisement appeal has positive relationship with effectiveness of advertising (Alam Z M., 2013). It was also determined that people set their attitudes towards objects on the basis of their beliefs, perception and knowledge about these objects These consumers interpret from the commercials accurate information (Kunkel, 2004). Saxena (1990) found those who addictive of from television advertising bought mainly brands and products more than advertised on TV. That represents more than 50 million teens in many of the markets and the impact on their parents' decisions taken in units purchased (Kurtz, 2008). Observations and Research verified that 73% of people to communicate with a family member at least for the time being by phone, e-mail, or even in person. In addition, it looks at the children also represents a huge and lucrative market, and a growing development for advertisers as they have the influencing power to the family purchase (Maher, Herbst, Childs and Finn, 2008). It is comprehended that commercials in urban areas in China affect the many fold of the purchase decision, either directly or indirectly (Caudill and Schodler, 1973).

However, many types of research have been done in the region and as well as worldwide to understand the commercials impact on shoppers' to understand the impact of advertising on their behavior. Still, there is a need to identify and quantify the factors that affect the behavior of buyers and their buying habits. Therefore, the present study is an effort in this direction. It is anticipated that this information will help the business community to learn about the different aspects of shopper behavior regarding the commercials. Besides, it would be useful to determine which should be the preference of the seller to deliver, implement promotional and commercial efforts to the desired parameter.

3. Objectives of Study:

- To assess the shoppers' behavior towards the commercials likability

- To identify the time spent on watching of television commercials.
- To know the opinion regarding the influence of commercial on purchasing decision
- To explore the attitude about product purchase after commercial show
- To understand the perception about the TV commercial benefit received by the respondents
- To investigate the impact of commercial influencing power to the family buying decision.

4. Limitation of the Research:

Although real effort has been made to put up for the study however, the following factors have been unavoidable absent because of their critical limiting factors for this study:

- Scarcity of time and cost
- This study could not cover all the factors advertising/ Commercials to see the impact of minors’ behavior
- This sample unit was restrained due to time and cost concerned.

5. Significance of the research:

- This study will be helpful to some business groups in general and particularly to KSA.
- The beneficiaries of this research is the international as well as the local community particularly in the related field of study
- This study will be helpful for the researcher for the further in-depth study.

6. Research Methodology:

The principal goal of the investigation was to know the impact of advertisements on shoppers and their influence on the buying decision. A convenience sample survey has been conducted of 160 respondents of KSA in 2017. While conducting the study, attention was given to reduce the non-response rate and the error arising out of it. After collecting the data, it was edited, coded and then recorded on excel sheet. For analysis, descriptive statistics (frequency distribution) were used, and result findings were interpreted to see the effect.

7. The Findings:

The respondents’ demographic information can be seen from the figure 1. Majority of respondents are male 75% followed by female 25% majority of respondents belongs to the age of between under 20 to 40 years of age (73.13%) followed by above 40 that is 26.87. majority of respondents are employed and about 80% of respondents has monthly family income between 5000 SR to 15000 Saudi Riyal (SR).

Figure.2: Opinion regarding Likability of Television commercials

Figure.2. Clearly indicated that 58% responded that they like to watch television advertisements while 42% respondents' said that they did not like to watch television advertisements.

Figure.3: Time spent on watching television

From the figure.3, it can be seen that in weekdays were the most spent time that consumer spent 1-2 hours while in a weekend majority of the respondents spent 2-3 hours in watching television. It can be interpreted from table 1 that respondents spent more time in watching television during weekends as compared to weekdays. During weekdays 30% respondents watch television for less than one hour but in weekends just only 5.26% respondents watch less than one hour. On the other hand, 17.37% teens watch T.V for 3-4 hours in weekdays, but in weekends, the percentage of watching television has increased about 34.21%. We can draw the impression from the result that in day's majority of respondents' watch T.V less than two hours but the weekend about 63% of respondents spend around one to three hours.

Figure 4. Indicates that responses of the respondents' regarding the influence of commercial on purchasing decision. 60% of the respondents were agreed that commercials had the impact of their purchasing decisions followed by 30% were neutral and only 10% said that there were no influence of commercial to the respondents. Over all this is an indicator that commercials have overall highest impact on influencing the consumer behavior.

Figure.4: Opinion Regarding the influence of commercial on purchasing decision

Figure.5: Opinion about product purchase after commercial shown

It is indicated from the figure 5. that majority 45% always buy the advertised products if they need it following by 35% said they sometimes buy not always its depend on the need of the time and related to the product they want to buy and 20% answered that they don't buy at all.

Figure. 6: Respondents opinion about TV commercials

As, it can be seen from the figure.6, most of the respondents have the positive attitude towards TV Ad. 79% of them are saying television advertisements create awareness, 87% are saying these provide information on product attributes, 73%% are saying adds demonstrate proper product usage while 74% consider television advertisements funny whereas 67% of them think that products shown in television advertisements do not fulfill their promise.

Figure.7: Perception regarding the impact of commercial influencing power on buying decision

It is indicated in the figure.7; that the television advertisement is having the good impact on shoppers and it has the influencing power to convince them always (54%) to purchase the advertised product followed by sometimes (30%) and never (16%).

7. Conclusions:

In conclusion, it is perceived that the advertisement has the significant impact on buyers, its buying behavior and influence on the purchase decision. Marketers are trying and focusing on attracting and controlling the shoppers by designing ads that are considerably attractive for them and persuasive enough for their emotional attachment to the product. The study identifies how respondents develops an attitude towards TV commercials and how it influence on the consumer purchase decision. The results of the survey provide reliable evidence that television commercials effects on respondents cognitions, attitudes, and behaviors. Shoppers is no doubt having the significant impact of TV commercials, and they like to watch television commercials. The finding very much convincing that most of the shoppers buy new products after getting information by the

commercial. Majority of shoppers do spend their time around 3 to 4 hours in the weekend on watching television. The advertisement also influences their buying decision while they shop. Most of the shoppers have a positive attitude towards TV Ad. Among a majority of them feel that television advertisements create awareness, provide information on product attributes, ads demonstrate proper product usage and consider television advertisements as funny, and entertainer but a high number of respondents think that products shown in television advertisements do not fulfill their promise. In addition to this, respondents noted that commercial has the real influencing power to convince always to their choices when they do consider the information when buying the products. We hope that this study will have vital importance for marketers to the positioning of the product as well as they can use this information to promote their product strategically.

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